

SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC IMPACT OF RELIEF SERVICES ON THE WELL-BEING OF EMERGENCY VICTIMS IN KANO STATE, NIGERIA

By

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Abstract

This study assessed the social and economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims in Kano State. The objectives are to examine the relief services provided to different categories of emergency victims; determine the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims; determine the economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims, and determine the relationship between social and economic impact of relief services provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency (KSEMA). The study employed a survey research design with population of 52,661 subjects comprising of 287 staff and 52,374 emergency victims benefitted from the relief services provided by KSEMA in Kano State. The sample of the study was 390 based on the table for determining sample size by Krejcie and Morgan (2006). The sampling procedure used in this study was a purposive sampling procedure. In this study therefore, the researcher deliberately selected and involved 30 Officials of KSEMA and 360 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services of KSEMA. However, in reaching out to the sampled beneficiaries a snowball technique was used. Two self-developed instruments were used in collection of data. These were a Questionnaire and a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide. While a 4-point Likert Scale type Questionnaire named "Questionnaire for Emergency Victims of KSEMA" (QEVKSEMA) for the emergency victims was used, an FGD was conducted with officials of KSEMA who were involved in the delivery of the relief services. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts. And the reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.074 was obtained. Data was analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics and discussed qualitatively. Findings of the study revealed among others that the relief services provided to the categories of the emergency victims are money, building materials, food items, non-food items, clothing materials, temporary shelters, medical facilities, agricultural facilities; artificial legs/arms, and walking aids, and there is significant relationship between social and economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims in Kano State. Recommendations made by the study include Government of Kano State should provide adequate security of lives, properties, and insurance of goods and services of emergency victims so as to facilitate their social resettlement in to their families, religious, and cultural activities, and government and non-governmental organizations should mobilize other sources of external

assistance/donations for supporting the provision of sufficient monetary donations that will facilitate occupational choices and career development among the emergency victims.

Keywords: Emergency, Humanitarian, Management, Relief, Social change, and Victims

Introduction and Background to the Study

Contemporarily, the scope of adult education transcends literacy, women education, and youth empowerment programmes to other aspects of social development that reflects on provision of services meant for the development of humanitarian activities and focusing on the promotion of the general well-being of the people. In Nigeria, prevailing emergencies include fire outbreak, insurgencies, flood, drought, desertification, and other forms of catastrophe requiring immediate responses. On January 21, 2012 Kano State started witnessing Boko-Haram attacks in places like the Police Headquarters in Bompai; Police Zonal Headquarters Kofar Na'isa, and the State Security Services Headquarters at Badawa. This has led to the death of many policemen and innocent people. Subsequently various attacks made on the convoy of the Late Emir of Kano on 19th January, 2013; the Kano Central Mosque on 28th November, 2014, the Farm Centre GSM market, Sabongari and Kantin Kwari markets. Fire out-breaks in places like schools, petrol stations, Dawanau, Kurmi, Kwari, Sabongari, and Farm Centre GSM markets, flooding in Bagwai, Wudil, Minjibir, Kibiya, Bunkure, and Kura Local Government Areas. Most of the emergency victims comprising of women, children, the old, and youths are usually vulnerable to poverty, hunger, frustration, crime, homelessness, unemployment, prostitution, and sometimes lost their lives and properties. At the onset of the disaster, the State Emergency Management Agencies (SEMA), the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), civil society organizations such as the Red Cross, along with international development agencies particularly the World Bank and the United Nations working with the Office for the Coordination of

Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) provided emergency humanitarian assistance to the affected population. Some humanitarian responses include immediate evacuation of the affected population away from flooded areas; relocation of the affected population in temporary shelters/ accommodation, provision of food, non-food items (NFIs) such as mats, blankets, and medical assistance to the affected people.

The Federal Government of Nigeria established the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) Act No. 12 of 1999 as amended by the Act No.50 of 1999 to manage emergency disasters. This policy therefore led to the establishment of the Kano State Emergency Management Agency (KSEMA) policy targeted on the provision of humanitarian responses of relief services so as to improve the well-being of the emergency victims. This paper therefore is intended to determine the relationship between social and economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims and draw implication on humanitarian development in Kano State, Nigeria.

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the Learned Helplessness Theory developed by Seligman (1967). The theory posits that animals and people can learn that responding to situation controls rewards and punishment. Human beings and animals are all sensitive to the independence of responding and reinforcers and can learn that events are either uncontrollable or controllable. The theory stressed three main effects of uncontrollable trauma which provided for learning in terms of response initiation, retardation of learning and emotional stress.

- i) Response initiation; that is the probability that the subject will initiate responses to escape is lowered because part of the incentive for making such responses is the expectation that they will bring relief;
- ii) Retardation of learning; that is learning that responding and shock are independent and which makes it more difficult to learn that responding does produce relief, and
- iii) Emotional stress; that is learning that trauma is uncontrollable may produce more stress than learning that it is controllable. (Seligman and Maier, 1976).

This means that people affected by emergencies can either make some responses or refrain from making it, and thereby influence the events around them. This implies that nature, however, is not always so permissive in its arrangement of the contingencies. Furthermore, they suggested that such uncontrollable events can be significantly debilitating them producing passivity in the face of trauma, inability to learn that responding is effective and emotional stress and possibly depression. The theory is relevant to the study as it highlights the situation of helplessness that emergency victims face. It also demonstrated the varying patterns of responses to the helplessness conditions including the response in terms of relief support/services. These therefore creates the need for interventional measures, through active relief services provision and which are expected to make them helpful and hopeful, as well as gain resettlement into their various social and economic lives and experience psychological stability. Furthermore, the experiences learned will allow for the emergency victims to have knowledge and skills as regards to disaster preparedness, management, and control.

Relief is an assistance provided to an individual(s) who experienced difficulties that require emergency responses. Relief services are programs which aim at assisting people in distressful

situations such as drought, flood, fire outbreak, and so on. Many programs are provided by various institutions so as to help the victims of disasters to deal with their immediate crises or situations in a way that maintains the dignity of the individual and encourages self reliance amongst them. This assistance through various services may take the form of food; utilities; transport; or pharmaceuticals, and cash to support payment of rent or bills, and sometimes other items such as clothing and household goods. Relief services involves programmes and infrastructure which required additional funding from other sources, such as donations, state/territory and local government funding, specialist service funding, and charitable trust funding (ACOSS, 2003). Relief service therefore entails a variety of supply of goods, services, and programmes which are meant to serve people whom experience various forms of distressful situations. The responses made are regarded as interventional measures to manage the vulnerability of such victims of disasters.

Emergency is an event, actual or imminent, which endangers or threatens to endanger life, property or the environment, and which requires a significant and coordinated response. Intervention to address disasters has evolved through time into a complex policy subsystem, and disaster policy is implemented through a set of functions known as emergency management and response. Modern approaches to emergency management and response involve multidimensional efforts to reduce our vulnerability to hazards; to diminish the impact of disasters; and to prepare for, respond to, and recover from those that occur.

Emergency victim is a person who suffered the effect of occurrence of disaster/event that disturbs his well-being in terms of loss of property, wealth, and psychological stability. Emergencies are unexpected occurrences that tremendously affect the lives of people requiring

an immediate response (Godwin and Paul, 2018). Therefore, the concept of emergency victim can be viewed as an individual or group of people who experienced disastrous situations which led to loss of life, property, or general well-being.

Statement of the Problem

Relief services are the immediate humanitarian interventions organized and provided for the purpose of helping emergency victims who were having social problems requiring adjustment in their various communities. Hence, many people lost their lives, some were injured and needs medical assistance, some lost their arms, legs and became crippled, women and children lost their husbands and became homeless roaming and participating in begging in the streets of Kano. The KSEMA was backed-up by an amended Act No.50 of 1999 to manage emergency disasters to formulate and implement policies that enhances the well-being of victims in such emergency situations through humanitarian service provision. Goods worth millions of Naira were provided to various categories of emergency victims. The aim of this is to enhance quality of life and improve the well-being of the emergency victims in Kano State. It is in the light of this, that, the researcher conducted a study to determine the relationship between social and economic impact of relief services provided by KSEMA and draw implications for humanitarian development in Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study are to:

- i. examine the relief services provided to different categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency;
- ii. determine the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency;

- iii. determine the economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency, and
- iv. determine the relationship between social and economic impact of relief services provided by KSEMA.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What are the relief services provided to different categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?
- ii. What are the social impacts of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?
- iii. What are the economic impacts of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

Research Hypothesis:

The following null hypothesis was tested during the study:

Ho1, there is no significant relationship between social and economic impact of relief services provided by KSEMA

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design with population of 52,661 subjects comprising of 287 staffs and 52,374 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by SEMA in Kano State. The sample of the study was 390 based on the table for determining sample size by Krejcie and Morgan (2006). The sampling procedure used in this study was a purposive sampling procedure. In this study therefore, the researcher selected and involved 30 Officials of KSEMA and 360 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services of

KSEMA purposefully. However, in reaching out to the sampled beneficiaries a snowball technique was used. Two self-developed instruments were used in the collection of data. These were a Questionnaire and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide. A 4-point Likert Scale type Questionnaire named “Questionnaire for Emergency Victims of KSEMA” (QEVKSEMA) for the emergency victims was used, an FGD was conducted with Officials of KSEMA who were involved in the delivery of the relief services. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts in measurement and evaluation, social work, and emergency management. And the reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.074 was obtained. Data was analyzed through descriptive statistics using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. While the data collected through the FGD with the staff involved in the delivery of relief services provided to emergency victims by KSEMA was reported verbatim and discussed qualitatively, the data retrieved and processed on the SPSS was presented in descriptive statistics in form of frequency (F) and percentage (%), mean (X) as well as cumulative mean score that indicated a decision from the analysis. However, the decision rule for the acceptance of the statement on items of the questionnaire was obtained by calculating $SA=4, + A=3 + D=2 + SD=1$ which was equal to 10 divided by 4 = 2.5. This means that a cumulative-mean score at or above 2.50 indicated the acceptance of the statement on the items of the questionnaire. As such any cumulative mean score below 2.50 justified statements on the items of the questionnaire were rejected. In addition to this, the null hypothesis was tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics and decision at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the relief services provided to categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

This research question was answered by the sampled emergency victims in simple frequency counts, percentages, mean score, and cumulative mean; where n=347.

Table 1: The relief services provided to categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency

Opinions of emergency victims on relief services	SA		A		D		SD		X
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Provision of counselling services	82	23.6	179	51.6	44	12.7	42	12.1	2.8674
Provision of housing	94	27.1	163	47.0	39	11.2	51	14.7	2.8646
Provision of food items	101	29.1	164	47.3	49	14.1	33	9.5	2.9597
Provision of home utensils	68	19.6	122	35.2	105	30.3	52	15.0	2.5937
Provision of clothing materials	70	20.2	183	52.7	55	15.9	39	11.2	2.8184
Provision of building materials	147	42.4	122	35.2	37	10.7	41	11.8	3.0807
Provision of medical facilities	84	24.2	165	47.6	55	15.9	43	12.4	2.8357
Provision of agricultural facilities	161	46.4	88	25.4	51	14.7	47	13.5	3.0461
Provision of capacity building materials	172	49.6	84	24.2	46	13.3	45	13.0	3.1037
Provision of monetary donation	126	36.3	84	24.2	87	25.1	50	14.4	2.8242
Cumulative mean= 2.8994									

Table 1 presents data on the opinion of the sampled emergency victims whom benefitted from the relief services provided by KSEMA in Kano. From this table, it was observed that 51.6% of the respondents agreed with the statement that provision of counselling services was a relief service provided to the categories of emergency victims. This was followed by 23.6% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. However, the highest percentage of 47 agreed with the statement that provision housing was a relief service provided to the

categories of emergency victims. This was followed by 27.1% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. In addition to this were those 47.3% of the respondents whom agreed with the statement that provision of food items were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. 27.1% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement. It was also observed from the table that 19.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that provision of home utensils were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. The highest percentage of 35.2 of the respondents agreed with the said statement. Furthermore, respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement that provision of clothing materials were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims constituted 20.2%. These were complemented with the highest percentage of 52.7 respondents whom agreed with the said statement. From this table also, respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement that provision of building materials were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims constituted 42.4%. These were followed by 35.2% of the respondents whom agreed with the said statement. Added to these were 47.6% of the respondents whom agreed with the statement that provision of medical facilities were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. This was followed by 24.2% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement on provision of medical facilities. Moreover, the highest percentage of 49.6 were those respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement that provision of capacity building materials were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. This was followed by 24.2% of the respondents whom agreed with the said statement. Also 36.3% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that that provision of monetary donation were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. It is observed that 24.2% of the respondents agreed with the said statement. These statements on

the opinions of emergency victims regarding the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims were accepted by the respondents. This was justified by a cumulative mean score of 2.8994 higher than the decision rule of 2.5000 in favour of the items in the questionnaire.

Research Question 2: What is the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

This research question was answered by the sampled emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by KSEMA in simple frequency counts, percentages, mean score, and cumulative mean, where $n=347$.

Table 2: The social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency

Social impact	SA		A		D		SD		X
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to religious activities	68	19.6	139	40.1	92	26.5	48	13.8	2.6542
Relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for sustenance of important/crucial social engagements such as marriage ceremonies, and festivals, etc	50	14.4	195	56.2	76	21.9	26	7.5	2.7752
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured full participation in community development activities	65	18.7	197	56.8	55	15.9	30	8.6	2.8559
Relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for Maintenance of family stability	82	23.6	138	39.8	105	30.3	22	6.3	2.8069
Relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged significant cultural activities such as appropriate mode of dressing, visitations, and sharing of goods and services	53	15.3	190	54.8	64	18.4	40	11.5	2.7378
Relief services provided by KSEMA facilitated leisure and recreation activities	50	14.4	133	38.3	118	34.0	46	13.3	2.5389
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to emergency education programmes	48	13.8	146	42.1	55	15.9	98	28.2	2.4150
Relief services provided by KSEMA enhanced access to health services	50	14.4	143	41.2	115	33.1	39	11.2	2.5879
Cumulative mean= 2.67									

From the above table 2, 40.1% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to religious activities. And a sound percentage of 19.6 strongly agreed with the said statement. In addition to this, the highest percentage of 56.2 was constituted by the respondents whom agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for sustenance of important/crucial social engagements such as marriage ceremonies, and festivals, etc. this was followed by 14.4% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement. Furthermore, 56.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured full participation in community development activities. These were followed by 18.7% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. However, 39.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for maintenance of family stability. This was followed by 23.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. Similarly, 54.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA encourage significant cultural activities such as appropriate mode of dressing, visitations, and sharing of goods and services. These were followed by a sound percentage of 15.3 strongly agreed with the statement. Accordingly, 38.3% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA facilitated leisure and recreational activities, a small percentage of 14.4% strongly agreed with the said statement. Added to these were those 42.1% of the respondents whom agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to emergency education programmes. This was followed by 13.8% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to emergency education programmes. However, 41.2% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA enhance access to health services. This was followed by a reasonable

percentage of 14.4 whom agreed with the statement. These statements were considered accepted by the respondents as justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.67 higher than the decision rule of 2.50 in favour of acceptance of the items in the questionnaire.

Research question 3: What is the economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

This research question was answered by the sampled emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services provided by KSEMA in simple frequency counts, percentages, mean score, and cumulative mean, where $n=347$.

Table 3: The economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency

Economic impact	SA		A		D		SD		X
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Relief services provided by KSEMA Created access to livelihood activities (occupations)	84	24.2	165	47.6	50	14.4	48	13.8	2.8213
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to income generation activities and maintenance for emergency victims	84	24.2	169	48.7	55	15.9	39	11.2	2.8588
Relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for increased access to financial institutions such as banks, micro-finance, money exchanges for emergency victims	88	25.4	142	40.9	71	20.5	46	13.3	2.7839
Relief services provided by KSEMA Facilitated transportation of goods and properties for emergency victims	56	16.1	113	32.6	110	31.7	68	19.6	2.4524
Relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for mobilization of external monetary donations and support to promote the well-being of emergency victims	65	18.7	148	42.7	66	19.0	68	19.6	2.6052
Relief services provided by KSEMA allowed access for reconstruction of infrastructure that ensured employment and promotes economic stability for emergency victims	64	18.4	153	44.1	60	17.3	70	20.2	2.6081
Relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged access to insurance of goods and infrastructure for emergency victims	51	14.7	114	32.9	116	33.4	66	19.0	2.4323
Relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to loan programmes from governments financial institutions	57	16.4	127	36.6	112	32.3	51	14.7	2.5476
Cumulative mean = 2.63									

Table 3 shows the economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by Kano State Emergency Management Agency. According to the table, the highest percentage of 47.6 agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA created access to livelihood activities (occupations). These were followed by 24.2% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. Added to these were respondents whom also strongly agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA ensured access to income generation and maintenance for emergency victims constituted 24.2%. This was complemented with 48.7% of the respondents whom agreed with the said statement. Similarly, while 40.9% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for increased access to financial institutions such as banks, micro-finance, money exchanges for emergency victims, a reasonable percentage of 25.4 of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement. However, the highest percentage of 32.6 was constituted by the respondents whom agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA facilitated transportation of goods and properties for emergency victims. This was followed by small percentage of 16.1 whom agreed with the said statement. Moreover, 42.7% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for mobilized external monetary donations and support to promote the well-being of emergency victims. This was followed by sound percentages of 18.7% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed for mobilized external monetary donations and support to promote the well-being of emergency victims. In addition to this, respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA allowed access for reconstruction of infrastructure to ensure employment and promotes economic stability for emergency victims constituted 18.4%. And the highest percentage of 44.1

agreed with the said statement. Furthermore, 32.9% of the respondents agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged access to insurance of goods and infrastructure for emergency for emergency victims. These were followed by a sound percentage of 14.7% whom strongly agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged access to insurance of goods and infrastructure for emergency for emergency victims. Added to this were those 36.6% of the respondents whom agreed with the statement that relief services provided by KSEMA encouraged access to loan programmes from government financial institutions. This was followed by 16.4% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement. These were justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.63 higher than the decision rule of 2.50 in favour of the acceptance of the statement in the items of the questionnaire.

Hypothesis Testing

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between social and economic impact of relief services provided by KSEMA

Below is the table for Ho1:

Table 4: Social and economic impact relationship

Variable	N	X	r	P	Remark
Social Impact	347	2.67	.679	0.41	SR
Economic Impact	347	2.63			

Table 4 above indicated a positive relationship between social impact and economic impact of relief services provided by KSEMA. Since the probability value is less than 0.05 level of significant. The calculated P- value is 0.041 which is less than the initial P-value of 0.05. This shows that the null hypothesis (Ho1) is rejected. And it indicated that there is significant

relationship between the social impact and economic impact of relief services provided by KSEMA.

Findings

From the proceeding data analysis, the following findings were deduced:

- i) The relief services provided to the categories of the emergency victims were money, building materials; food items, non-food items, clothing materials, temporary shelters, medical facilities, agricultural facilities, artificial legs/arms, and walking aids.
- ii) The social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA are having access to religious activities; sustenance of social engagement; full participation in community development activities; maintenance of family stability; significant cultural activities; leisure and recreational activities; ensured access to emergency education programmes, and enhanced access to health services by the emergency victims;
- iii) The economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA are having access to occupations; access to income generation activities; increased access to financial institutions; facilitated transportation of goods and properties; mobilization of external monetary donations and support; encouraged access to insurance of goods and infrastructure, and ensured access to loan programmes from government financial institutions by the emergency victims, and
- iv) There is significant relationship between social and economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims in Kano State, Nigeria, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of findings

The first finding of this study which is the opinions of emergency victims on the relief services provision that were provisions of counselling services; housing; food items; home utensils; clothing materials; building materials; medical facilities; agricultural facilities; capacity building materials, and monetary donation. This finding was similar with the findings discovered during the FGD conducted with the staff of KSEMA. When a discussion was held with the staff involved in the provision of the relief services to emergency victims in Kano State, and having identified the categories of the emergency victims. A question was asked “what are the relief services provided to different categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?” It was realized that “*the relief services provided to the categories of the emergency victims were money and building materials for the victims of fire outbreak; food items, non-food items, temporary shelters, and medical facilities for both victims of flood and insurgencies; money, food items, and agricultural facilities for the victims of drought and community conflict; artificial legs/arms, walking aids and medical facilities for the victims of automobile accidents and insurgencies as well, and money and clothing materials for the victims of armed robbery*”. This signified that relief services actively provided by KSEMA were based on what is available rather than what is ought to be available. However, in a study conducted by Enwemeka (2014) entitled the Administration of Emergency Relief Programme in Nigeria: A Case of Flood Incident in Delta State, the study justified the pattern of administration of emergency relief programmes in Delta State create management problems especially in ensuring equitable distribution of relief materials; there are evidence of inadequate facilities to ensure effective administration emergency relief programmes in Delta State and Nigeria in general; the needed manpower and technical know-how in disaster management are not enough to meet up

with the challenges in Delta State; the failure and inadequacies of administration of emergency relief programmes in Delta State is partially blamed on the poor funding of the government agencies charged with disaster management in the State; there is evidence of non-enforcement of some environmental management policies in reducing reoccurrence of flood disasters in Delta State; disaster or risk reduction and prevention planning in Nigeria especially in the oil-producing states is still low. This finding relates with the finding of this study on the distribution of the relief materials to the emergency victims not on the basis of their needs and aspirations. Therefore, there is the need for searching for sufficient funding of the programmes designed for managing emergency situations in case of the occurrences of situations that required emergency responses.

The second finding of the study which revealed that the social impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA were having access to religious activities; sustenance of social engagement; full participation in community development activities; maintenance of family stability; encouraged significant cultural activities; facilitated leisure and recreational activities; ensured access to emergency education programmes, and enhanced access to health services by the emergency victims. This finding is in line with the opinions of the staff of KSEMA involved in the provision of relief services to the emergency victims during the FGD. Accordingly, their response thus; the social impact of relief services on the well-being of the emergency victims as provided by KSEMA are *“been able to fully engaged in social activities such as attending religious congregations, festivals, and ceremonies; maintenance of family stability, recreation, dressing and make-up, and participation in community developmental activities by the emergency victims”*. Contrary to these responses were those findings justified in the seventh consecutive report by the Salvation Army in the national

Economic and Social Impact Survey (ESIS) 2018. The study is an adjunct to the ESIS 2018 report and is a summary of the main themes and key findings. This provided a deeper understanding of the experiences of hardship, with a particular focus on the cost of living and housing situations for those participants who accessed Doorways Emergency Relief (ER) services in Australia. The findings of the study revealed that a large proportion of respondents who accessed the Salvation Army's Emergency Relief services experienced financial hardship and disadvantage; homelessness and unemployment; inability to seek support from friends and family in a time of crisis; food insecurity; poor response to parenting responsibilities, and lack of and cost of transportation. The well-being of the beneficiaries of the emergency relief has been impacted negatively.

The third finding of this study which revealed that the economic impact of relief services on the well-being of emergency victims as provided by KSEMA are having access to occupations; access to income generation and maintenance; increased access to financial institutions; facilitated transportation of goods and properties; mobilized external monetary donations and support; allowed access for reconstruction of infrastructure; encouraged access to insurance of goods and infrastructure, and ensured access to loan programmes from government financial institutions by the emergency victims. This finding is in line with the findings from the FGD conducted with the staff of KSEMA whom justified that; *“the economic impact of relief services on the well-being of the emergency victims as provided by KSEMA are creating of occupational opportunities, engage in various occupation, increase in the income level, and having access to financial support among the emergency victims”*. The emergency victims in Kano State whom have benefited from the relief services provided by KSEMA have resettled back in to their communities and engaged in various occupations and realized changes in the levels of their

income. These were the results of having enjoyed various financial supports from banks and other external donor agencies whose main targets were to help the emergency victim's access services meant for supporting occupations and contribute to the GNP and per capita income of the general populace.

The last finding of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between social and economic impact of relief services provided by KSEMA. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that a significant relationship exists between the social and economic impact of relief services provided by KSEMA. The finding is in line with the findings reported in the study conducted by Enwemeka (2014) entitled the Administration of Emergency Relief Programme in Nigeria: A Case of Flood Incident in Delta State, the objectives of the study were to examine the relationship between the pattern of administration of emergency relief programme and effective emergency management and administration of relief programmes in Delta State; to ascertain whether administration of emergency relief programmes has really ameliorates the suffering of the flood victims in Delta State; to assess the effects of inadequate government policies on disaster management and poor funding on disaster management agencies in Delta State; and to suggest measures towards reducing occurrence and management of disasters as well as improving the administration of emergency relief programmes in Nigeria. Data used in the study was collected from both primary and secondary sources in which the primary sources. Findings revealed included the administration of emergency relief programmes in Nigeria particularly in Delta State has suffered a setback following the ineffectiveness of the public/government agencies discharged with disaster management and the pattern of administration of emergency relief programmes in Delta State create management problems especially in ensuring equitable distribution of relief materials. The study recommended among others that government should

provide adequate relief materials to flood victims in the flood prone areas in Nigeria and contingency planning which will provide preventive solutions such as construction of drainages and evacuation of flood danger zones to safer places.

Conclusion

It was observed that relief services rendered to emergency victims can impact not only on their well-being, but also on improving on their human capacities, hence, humanitarian support services can also arise from educational perspectives. Also humanitarian development during crises or disasters comprised of educational support services in form of literacy, vocational, and occupational training.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i) KSEMA should set a mobilization committee that will involve staff and stakeholders that will educate members of the public in disaster preparedness and management so as to effectively manage the occurrence of disasters in the State.
- ii) Government of Kano State should provide adequate security of lives, properties, and insurance of goods and services of emergency victims so as to facilitate their social resettlement in to their families, religious, and cultural activities, and
- iii) Government and non-governmental organizations should mobilize other sources of external assistance/donations for supporting the provision of sufficient monetary donations that will facilitate occupational choices and career development among the emergency victims;

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